

Multi-step Continuous Flow Synthesis of β/γ -Substituted KetonesSilvia Garbarino,^[a] Stefano Protti,^[a] Serena Gabrielli,^[b] Maurizio Fagnoni,^{*[a]} Alessandro Palmieri^[b] and Davide Ravelli^{*[a]}

Abstract: The smooth preparation of β/γ -substituted ketones has been carried out by a three-step continuous flow synthesis involving the initial photocatalyzed addition of an aldehyde onto phenyl vinyl sulfone. The resulting β -ketosulfones were then elaborated in flow to prepare *in situ* an enone upon basic elimination of the sulfonyl group and then to give γ -nitroketones, a 4-chromanone and β -(3-indolyl)ketones in moderate to good yields.

In flow chemistry the reactive components of the investigated process are stored in distinct reservoirs and then mixed together in a coiled reactor or a packed column reactor, where the reaction actually occurs and the product is continuously removed.^[1] This technique is particularly effective with respect to traditional batch chemistry, when the product (or an intermediate) is not stable under the reaction conditions or it can in turn interact with the starting materials leading to undesired by-products. Flow chemistry is characterized by a very efficient heat and mass transfer, a high reproducibility and scalability, the possibility to arrange multi-step processes and the use of in-line downstream processing. Overall, this technique is a powerful *viaticum* for discovering new chemical paths and allows to implement innovative and sustainable protocols.^[2] Over the last years, flow chemistry was applied with success to photochemical/photocatalytic reactions as well.^[3]

Scheme 1. a) Photocatalyzed acylation of electron-poor olefins under flow conditions. b) Multi-step continuous flow preparation of β -substituted carbonyls of type I (in bold the bonds formed). EWG = electron-withdrawing group. TBADT = $(nBu_4N)_4[W_{10}O_{32}]$.

In this field, we discovered that the photocatalyzed acylation of electron-poor olefins by aldehydes was smoothly carried out under flow conditions^[4] by using tetrabutylammonium decatungstate (TBADT; $(nBu_4N)_4[W_{10}O_{32}]$)^[5] as the photocatalyst (Scheme 1a). We envisaged that this reaction could be the starting point for the multi-step continuous flow preparation of β -substituted carbonyls of type I (Scheme 1b). The strategy relies on the photocatalyzed addition of aldehydes onto vinyl sulfones^[6] to give β -ketosulfones III. Base-induced desulfonylation^[7] to give enones II followed by reaction with a nucleophile (Nu) may give access to I with the overall formation of a C(=O)-C and C-Nu bonds. This sequence is of interest since volatile/unstable enones (in particular, vinyl ketones II) may be generated and derivatized *in situ* to form 1,4-difunctionalized entities.

At the beginning of our investigation, we focused our attention on the photocatalytic step. This was carried out adopting a flow photochemical reactor (**R**₁ in Scheme 2) previously used in our laboratory for the multistep synthesis of γ -lactones.^[4a] The reactor consists in coils of UV-transparent PTFE tubing (Algoflon PTFE; outer diameter: 1.6 mm; inner diameter: 1.3 mm, reactor volume: 12 mL) wrapped around a traditional water-cooled 125W medium pressure Hg-vapor lamp. Such lamp has a broad emission spectrum in both the ultraviolet and visible ranges. A Pyrex cooling vessel (able to cut all the wavelengths below 280 nm) was used to remove the most energetic components of the light emitted by the lamp, thus avoiding undesired side reactions. The reagents in solution were circulated by means of a multi-channel syringe pump (see Section 2 in the Supporting Information for further details). Under these conditions, the photocatalyzed acylation of **2a** to form ketone **3a** was investigated as the model reaction. The process (occurring in photoreactor **R**₁, flow rate: 4.5 mL h⁻¹) took place with a residence time of 2 h and 40' and **3a** was obtained in 63% yield. Interestingly, the product was isolated in higher yields under batch conditions (91%) by using a multi-lamp reactor (10×15W Hg lamp, 366 nm) as the light source, but the reaction required 40 h of irradiation to achieve a complete consumption of the substrates.

The first aim was the preparation of γ -nitroketones **5a-c** starting from aliphatic (**1a,b**) or aromatic (**1c**) aldehydes (Scheme 2). Thus, formation of ketones **3a-c** was followed by a base-induced elimination to form enones **4a-c**^[8] and Michael addition of nitroalkanes.^[9] As for the elimination step, tetramethylguanidine (TMG) was chosen among the different bases tested (see Section 3 in the Supporting Information). Thus, a TMG solution (1 M, 5 equiv.) in acetonitrile was charged in a reservoir and then circulated by means of a second syringe operating at the same flow rate (4.5 mL h⁻¹) adopted in the photochemical step. A three-way valve (**T**₁) was placed at the outlet of **R**₁ and connected with the TMG reservoir. A coiled reactor (**R**₂; volume = 10 mL) was then hooked at the outlet of **T**₁ and a new three-way valve (**T**₂) was inserted to connect the system with a reservoir containing the chosen nitroalkane (neat, 10 mL), circulated by means of a multi-channel syringe pump with a flow rate of 9 mL h⁻¹. The mixed solution was thus injected in the

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reactor **R**₃ (*V* = 5 mL) with an overall rate of 18 mL h⁻¹, to promote the desired alkylation. Reactors **R**₂ and **R**₃ were made of PTFE material as **R**₁. In order to ensure a constant flow rate, a back-pressure unit (BPR, set at 2 atm.) was inserted at the end of the reactor **R**₃ and the reaction mixture was collected in a flask, evaporated and then purified (see Scheme S1 in the Supporting Information). As described in Scheme 2, compounds **5a-c** were obtained in discrete to good yields during this three-step process, with an average yield (for each step) ranging from 80% to 87%. The main drawback of this approach, however, consisted in the use of neat nitroalkane (that acts both as reactant and co-solvent) in the last step, as well as the use of a large excess of TMG under homogeneous conditions, with the subsequent formation of significant amounts of waste.

Scheme 2. Three-step continuous flow preparation of γ -nitroketones **5a-c**.

We next investigated the chance to optimize the process by moving to partial heterogeneous conditions. For this aim, different supported reactants, as well as several reaction conditions, have been tested, and the optimization procedure is fully described in the Supporting Information (Scheme S2). The protocol that led to the best results is described in Scheme 3 and was applied to the preparation of compounds **5a** and **5'a**. In this case, the photochemical reaction was carried out on a 0.1 M solution of 3-phenylpropanal **1a**. A glass column, charged with polystyrene supported-triazabicyclodecene (TBD, 10 equiv., named **R**'₂), was connected to the outlet of the photochemical reactor **R**₁ and heated to 50 °C by means of a water bath.

A flow rate of 4.5 mL h⁻¹ was adopted for all the steps, and the reaction mixture was finally collected in a flask containing a stirred solution of the chosen nitroalkane (10 equiv.) in the presence of DBU (5 equiv.) in acetonitrile. The reaction course was checked by means of TLC and HPLC analyses and, upon reaction completion (1 h), the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude residue purified by flash

chromatography. However, contrary to what observed in the previous cases, **5a** was obtained in low amounts (20% yield overall) and considerable amounts of by-products (including a dialkylation product) were formed. Indeed, moving to 2-nitropropane as the nucleophile gave better results, with an increased efficiency of the process (38% yield over three steps), and only 4 equiv. of PS-supported TBD were needed to complete the elimination step.

Scheme 3. Preparation of γ -nitroketones **5a/5'a** by using polystyrene supported-triazabicyclodecene (PS-TBD).

In order to further exploit the multifaceted reactivity of enones **4**, we turned to the preparation of 4-chromanone **6d**, starting from a salicylic aldehyde as illustrated in Scheme 4a. We previously observed, however, that the activation of the (CO)-H bond in aromatic aldehydes is hampered by the presence of a phenolic group.^[10] Accordingly, we tested the *O*-Boc protected salicylaldehyde **1d**, as the starting substrate (Scheme 4b). In this case, the corresponding β -sulfonylketone **3d** was isolated in 52% yield under flow conditions. Furthermore, **6d** was smoothly obtained from **3d** in a one pot process, by connecting the photolyzed solution with a NaCl saturated aqueous solution of KOH (2.5%_{w/w}) by means of a Y-Mixer (**Y**₁). The presence of sodium chloride ensures, through the salting out effect,^[11] the formation of a segmented biphasic system that favored both deprotection of the *O*-Boc group and the β -elimination of the sulfone, to form **4d** that underwent spontaneous cyclization to chromanone **6d** under basic conditions, (35% overall yield, Scheme 4b). Interestingly, when the conversion of **3d** to **6d** was performed under batch conditions by adopting the same protocol, a complex mixture of compounds (including the desired product) was obtained (see section 5 in the Supporting Information). This protocol demonstrated both the opportunity of circumventing the presence of the phenolic group through a simple protection strategy and paved the way for the synthesis of chromanones, which are of deep interest for their rich biological activity.^[12]

Scheme 4. Two-step synthesis of chromanone **6d**.

Finally, we focused our attention on the development of a flow protocol for the acid catalyzed Friedel-Crafts alkylation of indoles *via* reaction with enones **4** (Scheme 5a). The interest in this reaction is due to the fact that the indole core is probably the most ubiquitous heterocycle in nature, since it is a leitmotif in many biologically active molecules, as well as an important building block of several chemical targets.^[13] In particular, substituted indoles are considered as “privileged structures” in drug discovery thanks to their ability to bind many receptors with high affinity.^[14] In this context, the 3-alkylation of indoles *via* Friedel-Crafts reaction with electron-poor alkenes,^[15] and in particular enones,^[16] is one of the most important derivatization strategies, due to the possible further elaboration of the functional groups introduced.

In this case, the photocatalytic step was followed by two sequential basic and acid treatments, making the adoption of supported reagents mandatory. We thus used the same apparatus described in Scheme 3, for the preparation of enones **4** under heterogeneous conditions. In this case, the solution coming from the photochemical flow reactor (6 mL h⁻¹) was connected to a column containing PS-supported TBD (**R**₂, 5 equiv.). A three-way valve (**T**₁) was placed at the outlet of **R**₂ and connected with the indole reservoir (1 equiv., 6 mL h⁻¹). The system was connected to a second column filled with Amberlyst-15 resin as the acid catalyst (**R**₃, 7 equiv.) and the resulting solution was finally collected, evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue purified (see Section 6 in Supporting Information). As pointed out in Scheme 5b, β-(3-indolyl)ketones **7-7''b** were isolated in 25-30% overall yield (60-70% for each step).

Scheme 5. Multi-step continuous flow preparation of β-(3-indolyl)ketones **7b**, **7'b** and **7''b**.

The set of examples reported in this work points out the potentialities of continuous flow conditions to perform multi-step processes. The present approach involves the coupling of an initial photocatalytic acylation procedure with other thermal steps. The preparation of the β-ketosulfone motif allows an easy base-induced *in situ* preparation of difficult-to-handle vinyl ketones, that were then exploited as coupling partners in different Michael addition reactions, occurring either under basic or acidic conditions. As a result, γ-nitroketones, a 4-chromanone and β-(3-indolyl)ketones were prepared over three steps by a highly versatile procedure. The yields over three steps range from 20 to 67%, corresponding to an average yield for the single steps between 58 and 87%. In particular, the preparation of β-(3-indolyl)ketones clearly highlights the advantage of combining flow chemistry with the use of supported reagents/catalysts, since it was possible to adopt two consecutive steps occurring under non-compatible/orthogonal conditions (basic for the elimination step vs acidic for the alkylation of the indole core). Indeed, the high versatility of flow chemistry allows to combine

thermal and photochemical steps, as well as the adoption of (catalyzed) processes occurring under heterogeneous conditions, and it is expected in the future to boost the diffusion of flow synthesis also for the preparation of complex molecules in a multi-step fashion.

Experimental Section

Typical Procedure for the preparation of β/γ -Substituted Ketones.

The chosen aldehyde **1** (1 mmol, 0.2 M) and phenyl vinyl sulfone **2** (1.2 mmol, 0.24 M) were dissolved in acetonitrile (5 mL) in the presence of a catalytic amount of TBADT (2 mol%, 0.02 mmol, 4×10^{-3} M). The solution was charged in a syringe, bubbled with nitrogen for 5 minutes and then pumped through the photochemical reactor **R**₁ made of coils of UV-transparent polytetrafluoroethylene tubing (Algoflon PTFE; outer diameter: 1.6 mm; inner diameter: 1.3 mm; volume = 12 mL) wound around a traditional water-cooled immersion well apparatus made of Pyrex. The resulting solution may be evaporated under reduced pressure to isolate the β -ketosulfones formed or treated under basic conditions (by a tetramethylguanidine solution or by polystyrene-supported triazabicyclodecene) to form the corresponding enones. Treatment of the resulting solution with a nitroalkane or an indole under flow conditions gave γ -nitroketones and β -(3-indolyl)ketones, respectively (see Sections 4 and 6 in the Supporting Information for details).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords Acylation • flow photocatalysis • ketones • indoles • radicals.

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Synthesis of β-γ-Substituted Ketones

γ-Nitroketones, a 4-chromanone and β-(3-indolyl)ketones were obtained by a multi-step continuous flow procedure, being the TBADT (tetrabutylammonium decatungstate) photocatalyzed acylation of phenyl vinyl sulfone the key step.